

ISic3115

I.Sicily inscription 3115

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

Metcalfe 2015.04.18

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

excavations 1974, via del Fante, adjoining Cooperativa S. Francesco

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR105958

1. Δαματρί [ου]

2. Ποπλείου

3. μακαρῖτα

4. χαῖρη (: χαῖρε)

Edition: PHI330070

1. Δάματρι

2. Ποπλείου

3. μακαρῖτα

4. χαῖρη.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284801

EDR 105958

EDCS 64800020

PHI 330070

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1075

Di Stefano, C.A. 1984. Lilibeo. Testimonianze archeologiche dal IV sec a.C. al V sec. d.C.. Palermo. At 178-179 no.193 fig.97

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1976. Su alcune iscrizioni inedite di Marsala.

Studi di storia antica offerti dagli allievi a Eugenio Manni. Rome. pp. 213-222. At 213-215 no.1 tav.10.1

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3115. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388149>